

EXPLORING SYNTACTIC COMPLEXITY AND SENTENCE VARIETY IN ACADEMIC ESSAYS: A CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS

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Exploring Syntactic Complexity and Sentence Variety in Academic Essays: A Critical Discourse Analysis

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Abstract

This study analyzed the syntactic complexity and sentence variety in academic essays of BS Nursing students enrolled in the Purposive Communication course at Our Lady of Fatima University Antipolo Campus using Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). The findings revealed distinct patterns across performance levels: the Above Average group effectively utilized complex and compound-complex sentences to articulate clear, cohesive, and rhetorically effective arguments, demonstrating strong syntactic flexibility and depth. The Average group predominantly used compound sentences, resulting in logical but less sophisticated essays with moderate coherence. In contrast, the Below Average group relied heavily on simple sentences, producing fragmented arguments with limited clarity and cohesion. The themes explored—clarity and argumentation, coherence and cohesion, and rhetorical effectiveness—highlighted the strong correlation between syntactic complexity and the overall quality of writing. Essays with varied sentence structures exhibited stronger argumentation, better flow, and enhanced rhetorical impact. The study recommends targeted instructional strategies, such as sentence structure workshops and focused writing exercises, to address these gaps and improve students' ability to produce cohesive and well-developed academic essays.

Keywords: *syntactic complexity, sentence variety, academic writing, critical discourse analysis, purposive communication*

Introduction

Writing is a fundamental skill in higher education, essential for expressing ideas, engaging in academic discourse, and demonstrating mastery of subject knowledge. In academic essays, syntactic complexity—measured by the variety and sophistication of sentence structures—plays a pivotal role in achieving clarity, coherence, and persuasive argumentation. However, many college students, particularly those in general education courses like Purposive Communication, often struggle with sentence variety, relying heavily on simple sentence structures. This limitation hampers their ability to convey complex ideas effectively, underscoring the need to analyze syntactic patterns in their writing and identify areas for improvement.

The researchers, who are students of Doctor of Philosophy in English and Literature and currently enrolled in a Seminar in English Grammar and Literature course, recognized the importance of applying the theoretical principles learned in the course to real-world instructional contexts. This study is an opportunity to address existing gaps in writing instruction by providing practical and evidence-based strategies for improving syntactic complexity and sentence variety among students.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED), through CMO No. 20, Series of 2013, mandates the inclusion of Purposive Communication as a core subject in the General Education Curriculum. This course, particularly in programs like the BS Nursing curriculum, aims to develop students' communication skills, including writing proficiency, as essential tools for professional and academic success. Writing coherent and complex academic essays equips nursing students to produce clear reports, reflective journals, and patient documentation—skills indispensable to healthcare practice.

Recent studies have underscored the significance of syntactic complexity in academic writing. Jagaiah et al. (2020) identified 48 syntactic complexity measures (SCMs), highlighting their variation across genres, grade levels, and writing abilities. For instance, argumentative essays exhibit higher T-unit lengths and more clauses per T-unit, reflecting greater syntactic variety and sophistication. Similarly, Casal and Lee (2021) found that high-rated essays demonstrate significantly greater syntactic variety, measured through global and phrasal complexity indices such as mean T-unit length and complex nominal densities.

Despite these findings, previous research has focused predominantly on advanced writing courses and specialized programs, leaving a gap in understanding how general education students, such as those in Purposive Communication, develop syntactic complexity. Moreover, studies like Maamuujav et al. (2021), Jiang et al. (2019), and Peng and Bi (2020) have revealed common challenges in syntactic complexity, including sentence boundary errors, limited subordination, and low lexical sophistication. These challenges highlight the need for instructional interventions that target syntactic elaboration to improve writing proficiency.

Pedagogical strategies aimed at improving syntactic complexity are also well-documented. Mostafa and Crossley (2020) and Demirezen (2019) emphasize the importance of sentence structure recognition and task-specific interventions in enhancing sentence variety and overall writing quality. These studies provide a solid foundation for integrating targeted instruction into courses like Purposive Communication to address the syntactic challenges faced by students.

This study is timely and significant as it aligns with SDG 4: Quality Education, which promotes inclusive, equitable, and quality education for all, emphasizing the development of essential communication skills. Additionally, the study supports the National Higher

Education Research Agenda (NHERA 2023-2028), which prioritizes enhancing instructional quality through research-based innovations. By analyzing syntactic complexity in student essays, this research addresses writing deficiencies and contributes to curriculum development that meets CHED's mandates and the professional demands of the nursing field.

This study analyzed the syntactic complexity in the essays written by BS Nursing students enrolled in Purposive Communication. By identifying sentence patterns, quantifying syntactic variety, and evaluating their impact on essay quality, the study aimed to propose instructional strategies that will enhance writing skills. Ultimately, this research aimed to equip students with the advanced communication skills required for academic success and professional excellence, aligning with national and global educational goals.

Research Questions

This study aims to analyze the syntactic complexity and sentence variety in the academic essays of first-year Nursing students enrolled in Purposive Communication this First Semester, Academic Year 2024-2025 at Our Lady of Fatima University Antipolo Campus. Specifically, it sought to attain the following objectives.

1. To determine the types of sentence structures used in the academic essays of the first-year Nursing students in the Purposive Communication course.
2. To analyze the impact of syntactic complexity and sentence variety on the quality of the academic essays of the first-year Nursing students.
3. To propose teaching strategies to improve the academic writing skills of the Nursing students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed critical discourse analysis (CDA), as developed by Fairclough (1995), to investigate the impact of syntactic complexity and sentence variety on the quality of academic essays written by first-year Nursing students. CDA is particularly effective for exploring how linguistic structures contribute to meaning-making and discourse quality within their natural contexts. The study examined the themes of syntactic complexity and sentence variety.

The study also conducted a frequency analysis, inspired by Silverman (2013), computing the occurrence of each sentence type. The sentences were categorized to explore the nuanced use of syntax in developing arguments and ideas, following the principles of text analysis outlined by Creswell (2014). This ensured interpretive depth and empirical rigor, aligning with established methodologies in discourse analysis (Dörnyei, 2007).

By employing Fairclough's CDA framework, the study aimed to determine the types of sentence structures in the academic essays written by first-year BS Nursing students, their impact on ensuring the quality of the academic essays, and propose teaching strategies to enhance the student's academic writing skills.

Participants

The participants of this study were 30 first-year BS Nursing students enrolled in the Purposive Communication course in the First Semester of the Academic Year 2024-2025 at Our Lady of Fatima University, Antipolo Campus. The participants were purposely chosen and categorized into above-average, average, and below average, based on their midterm grades, which adhere to the descriptive grading system. Therefore, there were ten (10) research participants for each group. This ensures a balanced representation in assessing the syntactic complexity and sentence variety in the academic essays of the BS Nursing students.

As first-year students develop their academic writing skills, this population is ideal for examining foundational patterns in syntactic usage and sentence variety. At this stage, students are actively transitioning into higher-level academic expectations, which provides a rich context for identifying areas of improvement and intervention. Moreover, their early engagement with the academic writing process offers insights into how program-specific strategies can shape their writing development.

By understanding the syntactic and stylistic tendencies of first-year BS Nursing students, Purposive Communication instructors can determine specific teaching strategies to address the gaps in writing proficiency and enhance students' ability to meet the demands of academic and professional communication. This aligns with the program's learning outcomes of fostering communication skills critical to the student's career success.

Procedure

The thirty (30) research participants were categorized into three groups of 10—Above Average, Average, and Below Average—based on their midterm grades. Participants were tasked to write a 500-word essay in one and a half hours. The focus topic was on the Philippine healthcare system, emphasizing the importance of understanding its various components and challenges. Students were asked to discuss key aspects such as access to healthcare services, quality of care, and the disparities between urban and rural areas. Their discussions should include the healthcare policies and programs that impact different communities in the Philippines. Formal language, a clear structure, and adherence to guidelines were emphasized to ensure the essays were well-organized, comprehensive,

and relevant to the topic.

The researchers collected the academic essays, pre-screening each to ensure they met basic criteria, such as adhering to the word count and providing sufficient content for syntactic analysis. This is to ensure that the essays were comparable in scope and focus. The essays were then collected and systematically organized. Each essay was assigned a unique participant identification code linked to the participant's group classification to facilitate data management and traceability while maintaining anonymity.

Finally, the essays were subjected to a detailed syntactic review, focusing on sentence complexity and variety to analyze the evident linguistic structure in the BS Nursing students' writing. This thorough data collection process ensures a robust dataset, enabling a comprehensive exploration of the syntactic patterns and stylistic features across varying groups.

Data Analysis

The study examined the essays of thirty (30) BS Nursing students from the above-average, average, and below average groups. Sentences were reviewed and categorized based on the four sentence structures: simple, compound, complex, and compound-complex.

The researchers counted the total number of sentences in the students' essays from each group and presented the overall sentence count for each essay. The syntactic complexity and variety were identified to highlight trends and differences across the three groups.

To analyze the impact of syntactic complexity and sentence variety on essay quality, the Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) was employed. The researchers critically examined the impact of the linguistic features on clarity and argumentation, coherence and cohesion, and rhetorical effectiveness. The findings guided the researchers to propose teaching strategies to improve the academic writing skills of BS Nursing students.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical guidelines were strictly followed to ensure participants' rights and confidentiality. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, emphasizing voluntary participation and full awareness of the study's purpose. Privacy was safeguarded by anonymizing participants' identities, and all data were securely handled to protect intellectual property and ensure its use solely for research purposes. The study adhered to principles of honesty and respect, ensuring that participants' dignity and welfare were prioritized.

Results and Discussion

Types of Sentence Structures Used in Academic Essays

Table 1. Data Extract 1: Total Number of Types of Sentence Structures

Participant Group	Participant ID	Total Sentences	Simple Sentences	Compound Sentences	Complex Sentences	Compound-Complex Sentences
Above Average	A1	50	10	12	18	10
Above Average	A2	48	11	11	16	10
Above Average	A3	47	9	12	16	10
Above Average	A4	49	10	13	17	9
Above Average	A5	52	11	14	18	9
Above Average	A6	46	10	12	15	9
Above Average	A7	50	10	12	17	11
Above Average	A8	51	11	12	18	10
Above Average	A9	53	9	13	19	12
Above Average	A10	49	10	12	17	10
Average	M1	40	12	8	12	8
Average	M2	39	11	9	12	7
Average	M3	42	12	9	13	8
Average	M4	38	11	7	11	9
Average	M5	44	14	8	12	10
Average	M6	41	12	8	12	9
Average	M7	43	13	9	12	9
Average	M8	45	14	9	13	9
Average	M9	40	12	8	12	8
Average	M10	39	12	8	12	7
Below Average	B1	30	15	5	6	4
Below Average	B2	32	16	4	7	5
Below Average	B3	33	14	5	7	7
Below Average	B4	31	14	4	6	7
Below Average	B5	35	16	5	7	7

Below Average	B6	34	15	5	7	7
Below Average	B7	36	16	5	7	8
Below Average	B8	33	14	4	7	8
Below Average	B9	31	13	4	6	8
Below Average	B10	32	14	4	7	7

This study analyzed the total number of sentence structures written by thirty (30) BS Nursing students from the three groups of participants: Above Average, Average, and Below Average. The results revealed distinct patterns in sentence complexity and frequency among the groups, providing insights into their writing skills.

The participants of the above average group consistently demonstrated higher overall sentence counts of (46–53) and greater use of complex and compound-complex sentences. This indicates strong syntactic flexibility and advanced sentence construction skills that reflect higher language proficiency.

The average group showed moderate sentence production with (38–45) sentences, having a balanced use of all sentence types. Simple sentences were slightly more frequent, suggesting that participants in this group were proficient but less inclined to employ more complex structures regularly.

In contrast, the below average group produced the fewest sentences (30–36) and predominantly relied on simple sentences, with limited use of complex or compound-complex structures. This reliance on basic syntax may reflect lower language proficiency and limited ability to construct varied sentence patterns.

The findings reveal that the below-average group's reliance on simple sentence structures reflects significant gaps in their linguistic proficiency, which is concerning given their level as college students who have completed two years of senior high school. Despite having foundational exposure to advanced grammar and writing skills during senior high, their limited use of complex and compound-complex sentences suggests having difficulty progressing beyond basic syntactic forms. This raises questions about their ability to meet the higher linguistic and academic demands of work, such as articulating complex arguments or engaging critically with written and spoken materials.

These results further suggest that the two years of senior high school may not have sufficiently prepared this group for the syntactic expectations of higher education. Their reliance on simple structures likely hinders their ability to express nuanced ideas, a core requirement for academic success. This correlation between their sentence complexity and language proficiency highlights potential gaps in their preparation and adaptation to the demands of communication and analysis.

Impact of Syntactic Complexity and Sentence Variety on the Quality of Academic Essays

This analysis evaluates the syntactic complexity and sentence variety in essays written by 30 participants, categorized into Above Average, Average, and Below Average groups. The presentation includes statements from 10 participants per group, analysis by themes, and a general analysis for each group.

Above Average Group

The Above Average group exhibited advanced writing skills, consistently using complex and compound-complex sentences to present nuanced arguments. Their writing reflected clarity, cohesion, and rhetorical effectiveness, aligning with academic standards.

Data Extract 2: Essay Sentences of Above Average Group

Participant A1: “The Philippine health care system faces critical challenges, particularly in rural areas where access to medical facilities is limited, but government reforms could help bridge the gap.”

Participant A2: “The disparity between urban and rural health care services is alarming, and it requires immediate attention to ensure equitable access for all citizens.”

Participant A3: “Although urban areas benefit from modern health care facilities, rural communities continue to struggle with poor access to essential services, creating a significant disparity.”

Participant A4: “To improve the current system, the government must prioritize rural health care by allocating resources and incentivizing professionals to work in underserved areas.” Participant A5: “By investing in rural health programs and ensuring equitable resource distribution, the government can address these disparities and improve public health outcomes.” Participant A6: “The lack of hospitals and medical professionals in rural areas highlights the urgent need for policy changes, which should focus on sustainable health care infrastructure.” Participant A7: “While urban centers benefit from modern health care facilities, rural areas remain underserved, resulting in widespread health inequities.”

Participant A8: “The government should create programs that focus on improving health care access in rural areas, addressing both infrastructure and manpower issues.”

Participant A9: “The unequal distribution of medical resources has led to preventable illnesses in rural areas, underscoring the need for systemic reforms.”

Participant A10: “A comprehensive approach that combines infrastructure development and community health education can significantly improve rural health care.”

The key themes derived from the data highlight the advanced linguistic and rhetorical abilities of the Above Average group, emphasizing their mastery in presenting clear, cohesive, and persuasive arguments within the context of the Philippine healthcare system. Below are the analyses of the three identified themes.

On clarity and argumentation, the participants in this group excelled in presenting clear, well-developed arguments. For example, Participant A3 used subordination (“Although urban areas benefit from modern health care facilities”) to contrast urban and rural disparities, creating a nuanced discussion. Participant A5, on the other hand, offered a solution-oriented argument (“By investing in rural health programs and ensuring equitable resource distribution”), maintaining clarity and depth throughout.

On coherence and cohesion, the logical flow and cohesion were evident in the writing of this group. For instance, Participant A1’s compound-complex sentence (“The Philippine health care system faces critical challenges... but government reforms could help bridge the gap”) effectively connects the problem with a solution. The consistent use of transitions and subordinating clauses helped create cohesive essays.

In rhetorical effectiveness, this group demonstrated strong rhetorical impact by combining advanced syntax with persuasive language. Participant A6’s statement (“The lack of hospitals and medical professionals in rural areas highlights the urgent need for policy changes, which should focus on sustainable health care infrastructure”) emphasized the gravity of the issue while proposing a concrete action plan.

The analysis revealed that the Above Average group consistently displayed mastery of advanced sentence structures, enabling them to present detailed and cohesive arguments. Their essays stood out for their clarity and rhetorical impact, effectively engaging the audience with well-developed points. The participants demonstrated a strong ability to connect ideas logically while addressing the complexities of the Philippine healthcare system, reflecting both syntactic sophistication and a deep understanding of the topic.

Average Group

The Average group relied heavily on compound sentences, producing clear and logical essays but lacking the sophistication of more advanced syntactic structures. Their writing was competent but less nuanced and cohesive.

Data Extract 3: Essay Sentences of Average Group

Participant M1: “The health care system in the Philippines needs improvement because people in rural areas often travel far to reach hospitals.”

Participant M2: “Urban hospitals are well-equipped, but rural areas are left behind, making it difficult for residents to get proper care.”

Participant M3: “Doctors prefer working in cities, and this leaves rural areas without adequate medical care.”

Participant M4: “The government should focus on rural health care by building hospitals and hiring more doctors for remote communities.”

Participant M5: “Rural areas have fewer hospitals, and many people cannot afford treatment when they travel to cities.”

Participant M6: “Urban areas have better facilities, but rural areas often lack basic services like hospitals and clinics.”

Participant M7: “The government needs to address the shortage of health workers in rural areas to improve access to care.”

Participant M8: “Rural health care requires more funding so that facilities can be improved and doctors encouraged to work there.”

Participant M9: “The lack of health care in rural areas is a problem, but the government can solve this by providing more resources.”

Participant M10: “Building more hospitals in rural areas and training health workers can help improve the system.”

The general findings on the three themes—clarity and argumentation, coherence and cohesion, and rhetorical effectiveness—highlight the writing characteristics of the Average group. Their essays demonstrated clear and logical arguments, moderate cohesion, and basic rhetorical techniques. A detailed analysis of these themes follows.

In terms of clarity and argumentation, this group provided clear and logical arguments, but the simplicity of their syntax limited the depth of their discussion. For instance, Participant M2 stated the disparities with clarity (“Urban hospitals are well-equipped, but rural areas are left behind”), but the lack of elaboration restricted the argument’s persuasiveness.

On coherence and cohesion, while the essays were moderately cohesive, transitions were often implicit rather than explicit. Participant M6’s sentence (“Urban areas have better facilities, but rural areas often lack basic services”) identifies a disparity but does not establish

broader connections, reducing overall coherence.

While on rhetorical effectiveness, the rhetorical impact was limited by their reliance on compound sentences. Participant M8 wrote, “Rural health care requires more funding so that facilities can be improved and doctors encouraged to work there,” which proposed a solution but lacked stylistic variation or persuasive techniques.

The average group demonstrated competence in constructing clear and logical essays, but the simple syntax is limited in exploring the topic deeply. While their arguments were logically presented, the lack of syntactic variety and rhetorical sophistication prevented their essays from having a significant impact. This group’s writing reflects a moderate understanding of the topic but leaves room for improvement in syntactic complexity and depth of analysis.

Below Average Group

The Below Average group relied almost exclusively on simple sentences, producing fragmented and underdeveloped essays. Their writing lacked cohesion, clarity, and rhetorical impact, failing to meet basic academic standards.

Data Extract 4: Essay Sentences of Below Average Group

Participant B1: “People in rural areas are sick. They have no hospitals. They need help.” Participant B2: “Hospitals are far away. People cannot get treatment. They stay sick.”

Participant B3: “The government should build more hospitals. Doctors should go to rural areas. This will help people.”

Participant B4: “There are not enough hospitals. Rural areas have no doctors. People need better health care.”

Participant B5: “The health care system is bad. Many people in rural areas are sick. They do not get help.”

Participant B6: “Hospitals are too far. People cannot travel. They need help nearby.”

Participant B7: “The government must help. They should send doctors. They should build hospitals.”

Participant B8: “People need health care. They are sick. There are no doctors.”

Participant B9: “Health care is important. Many people are sick. The government should help.” Participant B10: “Rural areas need more hospitals. People cannot get health care. They are suffering.”

The general findings on the three themes—clarity and argumentation, coherence and cohesion, and rhetorical effectiveness, highlight significant challenges faced by the below average group in academic writing. Their essays revealed struggles with presenting well-developed arguments, maintaining logical flow, and achieving rhetorical impact. The reliance on simple sentences resulted in underdeveloped and fragmented arguments that fell short of academic writing standards. A detailed analysis of these themes follows.

In line with clarity and argumentation, the participants in this group struggled to present clear, well-developed arguments. For example, Participant B5’s sequence of sentences (“The health care system is bad. Many people in rural areas are sick. They do not get help”), identified issues but lacked depth or elaboration, making the argument superficial.

Regarding coherence and cohesion, the essays from this group lacked logical flow, as ideas were presented in isolation. Participant B6’s statement (“Hospitals are too far. People cannot travel. They need help nearby”) failed to link ideas cohesively, resulting in a disjointed argument.

With the rhetorical effectiveness, the simplicity of the syntax prevented this group from achieving rhetorical impact. For instance, Participant B9’s statement (“Health care is important. Many people are sick. The government should help”) was repetitive and lacked the engagement needed to persuade readers effectively.

The Below Average group struggled with clarity, cohesion, and rhetorical effectiveness due to their reliance on simple sentences. Their arguments were underdeveloped and lacked logical progression, resulting in fragmented essays that did not meet academic writing standards. This group would benefit from targeted instruction in sentence structure, transitions, and argument development.

The struggles of the Below Average group with clarity, cohesion, and rhetorical effectiveness have significant implications, particularly when correlated with their level as college students. At this stage, students are expected to demonstrate a higher level of writing proficiency, including the ability to construct well-developed arguments, present ideas cohesively, and employ effective rhetorical strategies. However, the reliance on simple sentences and underdeveloped arguments suggests that this group has not yet achieved the expected competencies for academic writing at the college level.

This gap between their current writing abilities and the demands of collegiate standards raises concerns about their preparedness for the advanced analytical and communication skills required in their courses and future careers. Their fragmented essays and lack of logical progression indicate a need for further development in critical thinking and the ability to articulate complex ideas. These findings emphasize the importance of targeted instruction to address foundational writing skills, enabling them to meet the academic expectations of their level and equipping them for success in both academic and professional contexts.

Teaching Strategies to Improve the Academic Writing Skills of BS Nursing Students

Effective academic writing is essential for BS Nursing students to enable them to communicate ideas, think critically, and engage in professional discourse. The study revealed the results of determining the syntactic complexity, coherence, and rhetorical effectiveness among BS Nursing students' essays. The analysis of the impact of syntactic complexity and sentence variety showed significant findings on below-average students. They are struggling to construct nuanced arguments and maintain logical flow.

To address this, the following teaching strategies are necessary to enhance sentence variety, clarity, and cohesion in their writing, ultimately preparing students for academic and professional nursing communication.

Sentence Structure Workshops. Conduct workshops on constructing complex and compound-complex sentences, and effectively integrate subordination and coordination to articulate nuanced arguments.

Sentence Transformation Exercises. Use activities where students rewrite simple sentences as compound or complex ones, encouraging syntactic variety and the development of logical connections between ideas.

Thematic Writing Assignments. Assign essays on nursing-related topics (e.g., health care disparities or patient care) to engage students with real-world issues while improving their writing through critical thinking and topic relevance.

Explicit Instruction on Transitions. Teach the effective use of transition words and phrases to improve coherence and logical flow between sentences and paragraphs.

Peer Review Sessions. Facilitate peer feedback sessions where students evaluate each other's writing, focusing on clarity, sentence variety, and overall coherence, fostering collaborative learning.

Process-Oriented Writing Approach. Guide students through the stages of writing—brainstorming, drafting, revising, and editing—to help them refine their ideas and improve sentence structure progressively.

Model Essay Analysis. Provide well-written essays to show the effective use of syntactic complexity, clarity, and rhetorical strategies, then have students emulate these techniques in their writing.

Focused Grammar and Syntax Tutorials. Offer tutorials on common grammatical issues, such as combining clauses or correcting run-on and fragments that strengthen foundational writing skills.

Writing Prompts with Scaffolding. Start with simple writing prompts that gradually increase complexity, allowing students to practice sentence variety and coherence in manageable steps.

Rubrics Emphasizing Syntax and Rhetoric. Use detailed rubrics that evaluate sentence structure, coherence, and rhetorical impact, providing clear benchmarks for students to understand and improve their writing quality.

Conclusions

The study underscored the critical role of syntactic complexity and sentence variety in enhancing the academic writing skills of BS Nursing students. The differences observed among the Above Average, Average, and Below Average groups highlight the need for targeted strategies to improve clarity, coherence, and rhetorical effectiveness in student essays. This is aligned with the broader outcomes of the Seminar in English Grammar and Literature course, which emphasizes advanced grammar, textual analysis, and the development of writing proficiency necessary for academic and professional success.

Incorporating insights from the course, the study revealed that teaching syntactic structures such as complex and compound-complex sentences can significantly improve students' ability to articulate nuanced arguments and present cohesive ideas. This emphasizes the importance of understanding how grammar and literature intersect to create effective communication. This also reinforces the need to integrate advanced grammatical instruction with real-world applications relevant to nursing contexts.

Therefore, academic writing is vital for developing critical thinking and enhancing professional communication. Educators can help students overcome writing challenges by ensuring they are better prepared for the demands of their programs and the professional responsibilities they will face as future nurses.

Implementing comprehensive strategies that address the specific challenges BS Nursing students face in academic writing is important. Educators should emphasize syntactic complexity, coherence, and rhetorical effectiveness through teaching strategies in sentence construction, grammar, and critical thinking. These strategies should be integrated into the curriculum to ensure sustained development and alignment with the academic demands of their nursing program.

Writing tasks should be contextually relevant to foster meaningful improvement, connecting grammatical principles to nursing-related themes and real-world applications. This approach enhances student engagement and ensures that the writing skills apply to professional scenarios. Additionally, adopting a process-oriented approach to writing, which includes brainstorming, drafting, revising, and editing, can help students develop structured, coherent, and polished essays.

Lastly, a supportive learning environment is critical. Providing students access to model essays, detailed rubrics, and constructive feedback will clarify expectations and guide improvement. Peer review activities and collaborative learning opportunities can further enhance writing proficiency. These recommendations, ensure that writing instruction is rigorous and practical, preparing students for academic excellence and professional success.

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